

Trace Lead and Cadmium Analysis in the Effluents of MOENCO Garage, Feleg-Hiwot Hospital and Textile Factory in Bahir Dar, Ethiopia

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Received: July 23, 2015, Accepted: September 7, 2015, Published: September 7, 2015.

ABSTRACT

Environmental pollution is currently global problem and its issue is crucial. There are struggles to enhance advancement of science and technology in one hand and to play down its major consequence, environmental pollution, on the other hand. The present study aimed to determine the levels of trace lead and cadmium in the waste effluents of MOENCO Garage, Felege-Hiwot Hospital and Textile Factory in Bahir Dar town, Ethiopia. The analysis for lead was performed using FAAS and UV/Vis after extracting the metal from the given sample solution via complex formation by dithizone complexing agent. Colorimetric prediction also justifies where the concentration of lead lies in reference with the colour of the standards. The concentration of cadmium was determined using FAAS. Method significance for lead analysis was tested by F-test through the analysis of variance and the first separation efficiency was predicted from the recovery test based on the second extraction process. Besides to this pH, Temperature and TDS of each sample were determined. Based on the finding the concentration at the point source of their waste effluent for lead is: 0.45 ± 0.10 , 0.12 ± 0.10 & 0.31 ± 0.20 and for cadmium is: 0.021 ± 0.010 , 0.004 ± 0.002 & 0.031 ± 0.010 in ppm units respectively. The results show that the discharges at each site do have significant amount of trace Pb and Cd at the point sources. It is expected for the minimization of the trace metal pollutants along the ways through sedimentation and others.

Keywords: Trace metal, Extraction, complex formation

INTRODUCTION

Environmental pollution is a universal problem these days and studies concerning trace toxic heavy metals like Lead (Pb), Chromium (Cr), Nickel (Ni), Cadmium (Cd) and Arsenic (As) in waste water have a great role in this field. Manufacturing activities even in small scale industrial areas can introduce pollutants, like those mentioned above, into waste water system. One tends to associate the term pollution with materials produced by human activity that enter the environment with harmful effects especially on living organisms [1, 2].

Mostly those toxic metal forms are soluble in water and readily absorbed into the body system of organisms. The type of source commonly associated with pollution consists of either, part or both of the following: Industrial plants especially chemical factories using organic solvents and heavy metals, Mining's including waste rock dumps and smelters, Waste disposal dumps, Military bases from heavy metals as well as explosives and residues, Fuel storage factories and gasoline stations, Automobiles and other internal combustion engines provide a delocalized but abundant source and so on. Among all the expected sources, energy production and waste disposal takes the top rank in environmental pollution. Now a day's waste disposal is a growing problem. The environmental system consists of a very large amount of material: about 5×10^{18} kg of air and $1.5 \times 10^{18} \text{ m}^3$ of water [3].

Water discharged by different domestic and industrial activities can be categorized under waste water. It contains various inorganic, organic, and biological contaminants that are of

environmental significance. It can significantly pollute ground and surface waters when discharged without treatment [4, 5].

Due to the advancement of science and technology, the environment especially the atmosphere and the water body are largely exposed to pollution. Insufficient treatment or improper disposal of those wastes can vastly affect and even damage the living organisms. This is largely dependent on the degree and type of toxicity and its amount and concentration of the pollutants. If one looks, for instance, through domestic/municipal or industrial effluents its nature and property vary greatly.

Generally water, as a universal solvent, is used as a convenient source for waste collection, on the other hand, waste water is an extensive source of pollution if disposed untreated in to any natural environment like water bodies such as lake, river, and ocean. Hence proper management of waste water is a necessity, not an option. To plan and implement the type and extent of its treatment, studying about the kind and degree of pollution and the extent of toxicity of the pollutant is really a prerequisite. As a result this study intends to analyze environmental pollution due to trace lead (Pb) and Cadmium (Cd) toxic metals quantitatively from effluents of MOENCO industrial Garage (MG), Textile factory(TXF) and Felege-Hiwot Hospital (FHS) effluents of municipal waste water at Bahir Dar, Ethiopia.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study Area

MOENCO industrial Garage, Textile factory and Felege Hiwot Hospital are located in the Amahara region, Bahir Dar town, which is 560 km from Addis Ababa, capital of Ethiopia and the

exact location of sampling sites were indicated in (Table1). The industrial Garage, MOENCO, is the Motors & Engineering Company LTd. S.C. of Bahir Dar branch, Ethiopia. Its main actions are distributing and retailing company for TOYOTA and Daihatsu vehicles, Komatsu construction machinery, Case New Holland agricultural machinery, and various spare parts. Besides, washing the motors of vehicles and repairing damaged cars are the main activities. During its action from the garage industry, anti-corrosion metal compounds, metals which are additive in the gasoline and grease of the motors, battery wastes, discharge to the environment and this effluent may contain various metals like Pb, Cd, Cu, Zn and the like. The effluent of MOENCO Garage is

mixed to small tributary along the side of papyrus hotel coming from different sites of the town and leading to Blue Nile River.

The textile industry uses various pigments and dyes which contain metallic compounds like CdS, CdSe and lead compound dyes as an ingredient and bleaching powders made from metallic compounds [3]. And the discharge of the textile factory is directly disposed to Blue Nile River. The waste effluent of the hospital leads directly to Lake Tana. People use Lake Tana and Blue Nile River as a recreation site, swimming, irrigation for cultivation of vegetables and at a distant even for direct drinking purpose in addition to that of being a habitat for various marine organisms.

Table 1: Exact location of sampling sites (Taken from Google earth satellite image of Bahir Dar town, Ethiopia)

No.	Sample site place	Sample code name	Latitude / longitude Location	Elevation (m)
1	Hospital	FHS	11° 36' 28.76" N 37°22' 12.57" E	1798
2	Textile	TXF	11° 35' 41.01" N 37° 24' 27.76" E	1794
3	MOENCO	MG	11° 35' 12.75" N 37° 23' 07.50" E	1795

Instruments and Apparatuses

PH meter Model 3305, JENWAY, designed and manufactured in the UK, was used to measure the pH of sample. Mercury thermometer (0-50°C) was used to measure temperature of the sample. UV/Vis Spectrophotometer, Model SP60/SP65 SANYO, made in UK, was used for quantitative analysis of trace metals. Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer Model 210/211 BUCK SCIENTIFIC, for quantitative analysis of trace metals.

Reagents and Standard Solutions

Analytical reagents concentrated 68% HNO₃ (Spectrosol®, BDH, England), Lead nitrate (Pb(NO₃)₂) from BLULUX Laboratories PVT. Ltd. India, dithizone (H₂dz) from BDH Laboratory supplies poole, England, Chloroform (CHCl₃) WINLAB Limited, UK, Ammonia (NH₃) from BLULUX Laboratories PVT. Ltd., India, Sodium Sulfite (Na₂SO₃) from LOBA CHEMIE PVT. Ltd., India, potassium cyanide (KCN) from BDH Laboratory supplies poole, England, hydroxylamine hydrochloride (NH₂OH.HCl) from BLULUX Laboratories PVT. Ltd., India, ammonium Citrate ((NH₄)₂HC₆H₅O₇) from BDH Laboratory supplies poole, England, 37% hydrochloric acid (HCl) (Aldrich, A.C.S. Reagent, Germany), Cadmium metal (Cd) from BDH Laboratory supplies poole, England, potassium dichromate (K₂Cr₂O₇) and concentrated sulfuric acid solution were used.

Cleaning Procedures of Equipments

All plastic bags, polyethylene bottles, and all the other plastic bottle working materials were thoroughly washed with detergent, rinsed with water and then with distilled water. After that they all soaked in 10% HNO₃ for about 12 hours. Finally all of them were rinsed with distilled water and allowing them to dry before being used for either sampling or preparing standard solutions. All the glassware's were washed with chromic acid and rinsed with distilled water then allow drying in an oven adjusted 60 °C for half day.

Preparation of solutions and Standard Solutions

The standard solutions were prepared by common known techniques and according to standard procedures [4, 6].

Ammonical dithizone: 0.1% (w/v) of dithizone solution was prepared in chloroform (in amber bottle) and 6mL of this solution was mixed with 10mL of 0.5N aqueous ammonia.

Ammonia-cyanide sulfite: In 58mL deionized water 32mL of concentrated ammonia (NH₃), 7mL of 2% sodium sulfite (Na₂SO₃) and 3mL of 10% potassium cyanide (KCN) was added and mixed well.

Lead standard solution: 0.1599 g lead nitrate, Pb(NO₃)₂ (minimum purity 99.5%), was dissolved in approximately 200 mL water and 10 mL conc. HNO₃ was added and diluted to 1000 mL with water. (1.00 mL = 100 µg Pb or the solution is 100 ppm). This solution was used as a stock solution.

Cadmium standard solution: 0.1 g cadmium metal was dissolved in 12 mL of conce.HNO₃ (67 %) in three portions. This solution was dissolved with distilled water in 1000 mL volumetric flask up to the mark. The solution was 100 ppm used as a stock solution.

2% Sodium sulfite solution: 2 g of anhydrous pure Na₂SO₃ was dissolved in 100 mL volumetric flask with distilled water first in some amount then fill up to the mark.

Working standard solutions: These solutions were made from the stock solution through the process of dilution

10% potassium cyanide: 10 g of solid potassium cyanide was taken in to 100 mL volumetric flask and dissolved in 30 mL of distilled water and the solution was diluted up to the mark.

10% HNO₃ solution: 149.25 mL of conce. HNO₃ (67%) was added to 840 mL distilled water in 1000 mL volumetric flask and filled up to the mark.

Chromic acid solution: The solution chromic acid used as a cleaning purpose of the glassware was prepared by diluting 50mL of saturated potassium dichromate (K₂Cr₂O₇) with 1.5 L of concentrated sulfuric acid solution using 2 L beaker and a magnetic stirrer for thoroughly homogenization.

Sampling, Sample pretreatment, Preservation and digestion

Sampling

A preliminary survey of sampling stations was done for three days to select the appropriate sampling sites based on the access, objectives of study and the potential sources of pollution. Before collecting a sample, it was decided that only total dissolved metals has to be analyzed among the fractions (dissolved /TDS, suspended /TSS, total, or acid-extractable). The category of the fraction is based on whether the sample is acidified with or without filtration and the type of digestion required. Water samples from sampling stations were collected with 1 L-capacity polyethylene bottles, which have a suitable lid allowing for easier filling and removal of the sample, by composite sampling technique. Each grab sample to be composite was collected for 12 hours with one hour interval at each site. In this method, a small portion of water samples what it called a grab sample were collected at the point source or at the spots, where the potential sources of the effluents has to be expected, by tilting the bottle against the direction of the stream flow systematically and mix to the composite sample. Finally the samples were transported into the laboratory.

Pretreatment and Preservation of samples

Samples containing particulates or organic material generally require pretreatment before spectroscopic analysis. Hence, one third of the sample was reserved for physico-chemical analysis and the rest was treated for dissolved metal analysis as follows according to standard procedures [7, 8]. First, filter a blank consisting of metal-free (deionized) water to ensure freedom from contamination and then the sample was filtered using 0.45 μm type membrane filter into a beaker and then the filtered sample was immediately preserved by acidifying it with concentrated nitric acid (HNO_3) to $\text{pH} < 2$. The nitric acid used for this purpose was about 3 mL per liter of the sample. Finally all the samples were stored at 4°C until analysis in a refrigerator for maintaining the sample in a state that minimizes change in the composition or concentration of the components in the time between collection and analysis using a preconditioned plastic filtering device.

Sample digestion

A 100 mL of well-mixed, acid-preserved sample appropriate for the expected metals concentrations was transferred to a 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask in a hood, and 5 mL conc. HNO_3 was added. Boiling chips were also added to aid boiling and minimize spatter or bring to a slow boil and evaporate on a hot plate to the lowest possible volume (about 15 mL) before precipitation occurred. Heating and adding conce. HNO_3 was continued until a light-colored, clear solution was obtained, which indicates completion of digestion. The wall of the boiling flask was washed down with metal-free water and then filtered. The filtrate was transferred to a 100 mL volumetric flask followed by rinsing with two 5 mL portions of metal-free water, and this solution was diluted up to the mark of the volumetric flask. The solution was mixed thoroughly and it was then allowed to cool. A portion of this solution was taken for required metal determinations [7].

Some Physico-Chemical Parameters

Temperature: It was measured using a thermometer with a range of $0-50^\circ\text{C}$. The probe (or thermometer) was placed in the water to be measured.

P^{H} : P^{H} of the sample was measured electrochemically using a combination electrode (glass plus reference electrode) after calibrating against three commercially available buffer solutions.

Total dissolved solids (TDS): This is an indication of the amount of dissolved solids in the given sample and the quality of water as it directly affects the aesthetic value of the water. It is the residue obtained after evaporating the known amount of water sample in an evaporating dish to dryness at 180°C inside the oven.

$$mgTDSL^{-1} = \frac{(A - B) \times 1000}{\text{volume of sample, mL}} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where A = weight of dish and filtrate, (g)

B = weight of dish, (g)

Trace lead and Cadmium Metal Analysis

Analysis using FAAS

Operational parameters for FAAS (Wavelength, energy, lamp and burner alignment and slit width) were optimized for Lead and Cadmium analysis as in (Table 2). Then after, the prepared standards and the digested samples were aspirated in triplicates consecutively. The prepared standards were, for Pb: 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, and 2.0 and for Cd: 0.001, 0.005, 0.01, 0.02 and 0.03 in ppm units. At each interval of aspiration a rinsed blank (distilled water) was used to flush the uptake system so as to reduce memory interferences. The absorbance of the standard and the sample was recorded and the concentration of the sample was determined from the equation of the calibration curve using linear regression method.

Table 2: Operational parameters for FAAS

No	parameter	unit	For Lead	For Cadmium
1	Wavelength	nm	283.3	228.9
2	Current	mA	2.0	2.0
3	Slit width	nm	0.7	0.7
4	Energy	eV	3.805	2.884
5	Fuel	-	acetylene	acetylene
6	Oxidant	-	air	air

Analysis of trace Lead using UV/Vis.

The general procedure of lead analysis using dithizone follows extraction, colorimetric prediction and determination of the trace lead metal using UV/Vis at 510nm cut of wavelength [9, 10, 11]. In a 250 mL separatory funnel 2 mL of Pb^{+2} standard or digested samples, 2 mL of 1N HCl solution, 0.2 g of hydroxyl ammine hydrochloride and 1 g ammonium citrate were added and mixed well. And then to this mixture 30 mL of ammonia cyanide sulfite reagent, 10 mL chloroform and 0.5 mL ammonical dithizone were added and the solution was shaken well for one minute and allowed forming layer.

In the process, the media was made alkaline ($\text{pH} 10$ to 11.5) by the formation of ammonium buffer from the added reagents in situ via the reaction media. At this medium dithizone, doesn't react with alkali and alkaline earth metals, but it can form a complex with many other cations. To prevent this cyanide ion was introduced to mask many of the cations (like Ag^+ , Hg^{+2} , Cu^{+2} , Zn^{+2} , Cd^{+2} , Ni^{+2} , and Co^{+2}) by forming stable cyanide complexes. And the precipitation of readily hydrolyzing metals has been prevented by introducing citrate ion into the solution prior to the extraction of lead-dithizone complex using chloroform organic solvent. In a weakly ammonical cyanide solution ($\text{pH} 8.5$ to 9.5) dithizone can also form colored complexes with bismuth, stannous tin and monovalent thallium. But in strongly ammonical citrate-cyanide solution ($\text{pH} 10$ to 11.5) the dithizonates of these

ions are unstable. Besides, hydroxyl ammine hydrochloride was used as a reducing agent since dithizone is easily oxidized [7, 10, 11].

A cotton plug was inserted in to the stem of the funnel and opens the stopcock. The extract coming out from the stem was collected in a receiver and this was analysed using UV/Vis spectrophotometer

Lead dithizonate complex analysed using UV/Vis spectrophotometer at about 510nm cut of wavelength [11]. Basing the high range of linearity for the purpose of applying the beer's law and for the colorimetric prediction of the sample the following standards were prepared from analytical grade lead (II) nitrate. The prepared standards were: 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 5.0, 7.0, 10.0, 15.0 and 20.0 in ppm units.

Separation Efficiency: Separation efficiency is influenced both by the failure to recover all the analyte and the failure to remove all the interferent in principle. Hence the performance of the separation process was estimated using recovery test. Recovery (R) is the fraction of analyte or interferent remaining after a separation. Here spiking experiments were employed to validate the separation process. Accordingly, 5 ppm of known amount standard were processed first and second extraction in the same manner for the other standards and samples and the amount of analyte obtained from the second extraction was determined using

Table 3: Values of physico-chemical variables

No	variables	unit	Sample site		
			MG	FHS	TXF
1	Temperature	°c	19.3 ± 3.8	17.3 ± 3.8	18.7 ± 5.2
2	pH	pH units	8.09 ± 0.35	6.48 ± 0.57	8.15 ± 0.45
3	TDS	mg/L	968.8 ± 13.43	986.5 ± 8.02	973.1 ± 7.0

Note: measured results (μ) are average of triplicate measurements at 95% confidence level.

$$\mu = \frac{\text{mean} \pm \frac{ts}{\sqrt{n}}}{\dots} \dots \dots (2)$$

Where: s = standard deviations of the measured values.
t = statistical factor whose value is determined by the number of samples and the desired confidence level, in this case its value is 4.3.

n = number of replicate measurements of the sample

Concentration of Trace Lead and Cadmium using FAAS

Lead: The concentration of lead using AAS was determined from linear equation obtained by the calibration curve of the standards 0.1, 0.5, 1.0 and 2.0 ppm as in (Figure 1 and Equ.3).

Fig.1 Calibration curve for standards of lead using FAAS.

UV/Vis. This result was used to predict the recovery of the first extraction process.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results of physico-Chemical Parameters

(Table 3) shows some physico-chemical parameters in the samples. The temperatures for all samples were relatively the same through the study period. It is important parameter, which regulates various biochemical reaction rates and concentration of oxygen dissolved in water [12, 13]. The temperature of samples was in the range from 18.7 - 19.3 (°c) in both three sites.

Acidity or alkalinity, which was measured by pH-meter, has important effect on potential toxicants; like the bioavailability of heavy metals because the behavior of ions and organic compounds is directly related with the pH value [14]. It was found that the pH-value of three sampling sites was range between 6.48 -8.15 units. The results revealed that at two sample sites, which is MG and TXF the PH resembles to alkalinity.

The TDS in waste effluent represents the colloidal form and dissolved species [4]. The TDS was 968.8 ± 13.43 , 986.5 ± 8.02 and 973.1 ± 7.0 mg/L. of MG, FHS and TXF effluent respectively.

Table 4: Linear Regression values for the calibration curve of lead standards using FAAS,

Parameter	Value	Error
A	0.00196	5.65557 x 10 ⁻⁴
B	0.01421	4.9319 x 10 ⁻⁴
R	SD	N
0.9988	7.00954 x10 ⁻⁴	4

Where A=y intercept, B= the slope of the line, R= regression, SD, standard deviation.

And the linear equation of the curve is

$$y = A + Bx \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Cadmium: The concentration of cadmium was determined using the linear equation obtained by the calibration curve produced from the standards 0.001, 0.005, 0.01, 0.02 and 0.03 ppm units as in (Figure 2 and Equ.3).

Fig.2: Calibration curve for standards of Cadmium using FAAS.

B= 0.5 ppm G= 7 ppm
 C=1 ppm H= 10 ppm
 D= 2 ppm I= 15 ppm
 E= 3 ppm J= 20 ppm,
 And the other three are the samples from each site.

For the determination of trace lead using UV/Vis via linear regression, its calibration curve from the standards is shown in (figure 4) and the linear equation of the curve is just as (Equ.3).

Table 5: Linear Regression for the calibration curve of cadmium standards using FAAS

Parameter	Value	Error
A	0.0016	2.03133 x 10 ⁻⁴
B	0.43908	
R	SD	N
0.99888	2.83318 x 10 ⁻⁴	5

Based on these two calibration equations the concentration of lead and cadmium were determined from each sample absorbance and the corresponding results were listed in (Table 6).

Table 6: Concentration of lead and cadmium in the samples taken at the point source of each site using FAAS determination.

No	Sample Site	Concentration (ppm)	
		lead	cadmium
1	MG	0.45 ± 0.10	0.021 ± 0.010
2	FHS	0.12 ± 0.10	0.004 ± 0.002
3	TXF	0.31 ± 0.20	0.031 ± 0.010

Measured results (μ) are average of triplicate measurements at 95% confidence level.

Concentration of trace Lead using UV/Vis

From the prepared standard solutions, separation of lead from each standard has been done and various coloured solutions were obtained. The colour of the samples through comparison lies between the colour of the standards of 0.1 and 0.5 ppm, as shown in (Figure 3).

Fig.3: Colorimetric prediction of the samples based on the standards.

Where: A-J = standards with a concentration of
 A= 0.1 ppm F= 5 ppm

Fig.4: Calibration curve for standards of lead using UV/Vis.

Table 7: Linear Regression for the calibration curve of lead standards using UV/Vis,

Parameter	Value	Error
A	0.16379	0.00832
B	0.07263	0.00182
R	SD	N
0.99781	0.01793	9

Table 8: Concentration of Lead from the analysis of UV/Vis

No	Sample Site	Concentration of Pb (ppm)
1	MG	0.43 ± 0.05
2	FHS	0.10 ± 0.05
3	TXF	0.29 ± 0.05

Measured results (μ) are average of triplicate measurements at 95% confidence level.

Validation of the methods

Recovery of the separation Process

Analytical separation was used to remove either the analyte or the interferent from the sample matrix. But a separation that completely removes an interferent may result in the partial loss of analyte. Altering the separation to minimize the loss of analyte, however, may leave behind some of the interferent. Hence separation efficiency is influenced both by the failure to recover all the analyte and the failure to remove all the interferent. The analytes recovery (R) is defined as the fraction of analyte remaining after a separation. [11]

That is:

$$R = \frac{C_A}{(C_A)_o} \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

Where: C_A = the concentration of analyte remaining after the separation, and $(C_A)_o$ = the analytes initial concentration.

A recovery of 1.00 means none of the analyte is lost during the separation. It is possible to express this value as percentage by multiplying with 100 [11]. Based on the procedures the concentration of Pb obtained from the absorbance of the second extraction of the known standard 5 ppm on average is 0.31 ppm units. Hence the total amount of the analyte that can recover is the difference from the original standard 5 ppm, which is 4.69, and hence the recovery of the separation process is 0.938 or 93.8%. Besides to this the colour of the second extracted solution is comparable with the colour of the extracted solution by the use of distilled water which is simply the colour of dithizone chloroform solution as shown in (Figure 4). The procedure with the use of distilled water is similar to the others.

Fig.5: The extraction processes using separatory funnel for colour comparison.

Where: A= the colour of the complex for the 1st extraction of 5ppm standard.

B= the colour of the solution for the 2nd extraction of 5ppm standard

C= the colour obtained by the use of distilled water.

Significance of the methods

In deciding weather one set of result is significantly different from another depends not only on the difference in the means but also on the amount of the data available and the spread. There are tests designed to indicate whether there is a significance difference or not between results of two methods on identical sample. Among them one is the F-test that forms analysis on the variance of the results to show either they are statistically different or identical. The calculated value of 'F' can be obtained by:

$$F = \frac{S_1^2}{S_2^2} \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

Where: S_1^2 = variance of the 1st statistical data.

S_2^2 = variance of the 2nd statistical data; and the variances should be arranged to get F value greater than one, that is $S_1^2 > S_2^2$.

If the calculated F value from equation (5) exceeds a tabulated F value at the selected confidence level, then there is a significance difference between the variances of the two methods, otherwise, if the reverses case is true, there is no significance difference in the precision of the two methods. In this case the difference is only derived from random errors alone [15, 16]. Based on this, the data's of the results of lead analysed by AAS and UV/Vis are calculated and recorded by the following table so as to compare it easily.

Table 9: Calculated values of F for the analysis of Lead using AAS and UV/Vis

No.	Sample Site	AAS	UV/Vis	AAS	UV/Vis	$F = \frac{S_1^2}{S_2^2}$
		$\bar{X} \pm \frac{ts}{\sqrt{n}}$	$\bar{X} \pm \frac{ts}{\sqrt{n}}$	S_1^2	S_2^2	
1	MG	0.45 ± 0.10	0.43 ± 0.05	0.0016	0.0004	4
2	FHS	0.12 ± 0.10	0.10 ± 0.05	0.0016	0.0004	4
3	TXF	0.31 ± 0.20	0.29 ± 0.05	0.0064	0.0004	16

Where: $\bar{X} \pm \frac{ts}{\sqrt{n}}$ = measured values of average of triplicate measurements at 95% confidence level.

Note: The tabulated value of F at the 95 % confidence level and for 2 degrees of freedom in both data is 19.0 [16].

As it can be seen clearly from table 12 the F value calculated for each site is less than the tabulated value of F for two degrees of freedom at 95% confidence level, hence the results obtained by the two methods does not have significance difference.

Comparison of the Results Among each site

The values obtained from each site calculated at the 95 % confidence level can be compared directly by the following bar graph.

Fig.6: Concentration of Pb at each site.

As it can be seen from the bar graphs clearly the least polluted effluent comes out from the hospital site. In their lead concentration, MG takes the highest rank while to that of cadmium TXF is the leading, in comparisons among each other.

Comparison of the Results of this work with the Standard Values

Different countries and international institutions or organizations do have standard values of the levels of Pb and Cd

Fig.7: Concentration of Cd at each site

that can be discharged with wastewater. But the permissible standards also vary with the use and/or impact of the wastewater after treatment. As it can be seen from the bar graph and the horizontal line the level of the trace metals in the sample taken from MG and TXF exceeds the permissible limits given by the organizations like FAO and CPCB. Some other such standards are tabulated additionally for compression as in (Table 10) [7, 17, 18].

Table 10: Permissible levels of Pb and Cd in Wastewater

No.	Use of wastewater	Permissible level (ppm)		Organization
		Pb	Cd	
1	Finished effluent from textile	0.5	1	Ethiopia
2	For irrigation	0.5	0.01	FAO
3	For irrigation	0.02	0.005	Middle east
4	For irrigation	5.00	0.01	EPA
5	For drinking water	0.01	0.003	WHO
6	Effluent to public sewers	1.0	1.0	CPCB/India
7	For farm animal	0.05	0.01	NTAC/India
8	For live stock	0.1	0.05	NTAC/India
9	Effluent to inland surface water	0.1	2.0	CPCB/India

Though the results of the study is at the point of the source, and as a result there may be a chance to play down along its way through sedimentation and other factors, relative to some organizations the concentration of lead and cadmium discharged from each site may have chances to be at a higher level than the permissible amount. Additionally the amount of Cadmium Present in wastewater used for irrigation is still above the permissible limit given by FAO as it can be seen clearly by the horizontal lines in fig. 14 and 15.

CONCLUSION

Now a day, environmental pollution is a crucial issue and it sounds globally. Due to its consequence no one has to leave behind, it should be the agenda of everyone. Among the sources of pollutants, effluents from industrial technology are the most common. Municipal and domestic effluents can also be the source of pollutants. Testing for trace metal in the discharges of such pollutant sources that pilot to fresh water is imperative as fresh water is used by living organisms especially by human beings in one or another way. Hence the present finding on the analysis of trace lead and cadmium in the given study sites is really

fundamental and essential. Based on the finding at the point source; the concentration of lead is high in MG, and the concentration of cadmium is high in TXF in relation with each other. And the discharge from FHS is less polluted by both metals. Generally the findings show that the discharges at each site do have significant amount of trace Pb and Cd at the point sources. Hence, though it is expected for the minimization of the trace metal pollutants along the ways through sedimentation and others, using the effluent water for various purposes like watering vegetables, using by farm animals or adding these effluents directly in to fresh water may have an adverse effect.

The sources of the pollutant trace Pb and Cd in MG may be gasoline as a waste from washing activities especially of the engines, pigments for painting the bodies of cars and maintenance activities. In case of TXF the pigments for dying purpose can be the possible sources of such trace metals, and for FHS the biological samples like urine and blood and certain medicines that may have additive either naturally or deliberately of such metals may be the possible sources. All study sites (MG, TXF and FHS) should have to build a nice trace metal treatment plantation. The treatment plantations for instance can be sedimentation process

with the use of clay soil [19] or other chemicals like H₂O₂ and FeCl₃ and/or allowing the discharge to pass through scavenger plants that are not edible what named biologically phyto-technology.

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Citation: Marie Yayinie et al.. (2015) Trace Lead and Cadmium Analysis in the Effluents of MOENCO Garage, Feleg-Hiwot Hospital and Textile Factory in Bahir Dar, Ethiopia. *J. of Physical and Chemical Sciences*.V3I3. DOI: 10.15297/JPCS.V3I3.01

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